

Mediation Effect of Job Satisfaction and Job Stress on Leader-Member Exchange Relationship on Turnover Intention of Hotel Employees in Banda ACEH

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Abstract: This study aims to analyze the effect of leader-member exchange (LMX) on turnover intentions mediated by job satisfaction and job stress of hotel employees in Banda Aceh. This research was conducted at the Ayani Hotel, Grand Nanggroe, Grand Permata Hati Hotel, and The Pade Hotel with a total population of 213 people. The sample was determined a saturated sample technique. Data were collected by distributing questionnaires and analyzed using AMOS SEM statistical equipment. The result proves that the LMX positively affects satisfaction, but negatively affects job stress and turnover intention; satisfaction negatively affects turnover intention; job stress positively affects turnover intention; satisfaction and job stress partially mediate the LMX effect on turnover intention. This finding proves that the model of decreasing turnover intention for hotel employees in Banda Aceh is a function of increasing LMX which can contribute to increasing job satisfaction and reducing job stress.

Keywords: Leader-Member Exchange, Job Satisfaction, Job Stress, Turnover Intention

I. Introduction

Within the scope of company operations, turnover often occurs. The occurrence of turnover is beyond the control of the company. Turnover is a problem in human resource management faced by the company. Turnover activities have an impact on various work activities in the company and can also have an impact on the overall work performance of employees.

(Gerstner & Day, 1997) validated in their research that the high quality of the leader-member exchange (LMX) makes it easier to achieve ideal work results, improve performance, and reduce employee turnover intention. (Bauer, Erdogan, Liden, & Wayne, 2006) stated regarding the relationship between turnover intentions and LMX that members who have low-quality LMX may have an unfavorable relationship with their leader, so they may have a greater intention to leave than the quality of leader-member high exchange rate. (Shen, Jackson, Ding, & Yuan, 2014) stated that the LMX is an increase in the quality of the relationship between superiors and employees, but in reality, the relationship between superiors and employees is not always good so it can result in employees not being able to last long to work for the company.

The desire to move is associated with job satisfaction and job stress. This is because employees in a company who have satisfaction are more productive, contribute to company goals and have a low level of desire to move from the company (Harter, Schmidt, & Hayes, 2002). While dissatisfaction occurs when an employee has thoughts of leaving his job because by leaving his job, the employee hopes to get another job that can provide better satisfaction.

Another factor that affects employee turnover is job stress. The COVID-19 pandemic has put a lot of stress on everyone. Fear and anxiety about the covid pandemic plus other factors can affect job stress. (Hamouche, 2020) states that during the COVID-19 pandemic, many stressors can cause mental health problems in workers both during and after the pandemic. Stress during the pandemic consists of the threat of transmission risk, safety perceptions, incorrect information, quarantine, and working conditions. Research conducted by (Hwang, Lee, Park, Chang, & Kim, 2014) on 330 employees of 5-star hotels in Seoul, Korea stated that there are job stress factors that predict the occurrence of turnover intentions in hotel employees.

This study is intended for employees of three-star hotels because three-star hotels are in the middle level of hotel grouping based on stars, so employees have the desire to move to hotels with higher levels. Employees think that four-star and five-star hotels offer higher levels of employee well-being. Competition between hotels is also

getting tougher. Where hotel employee recruitment is selected based on qualifications, one of which has experience in the hospitality sector. So it is not uncommon for hotel employees to think about turnover intentions to a higher-level hotel because they feel they already have experience and have mastered skills in the hospitality world.

II. Literature

Leader-Member Exchange (LMX)

According to (Graen & Uhl-Bien, 1995) LMX consists of a leader (superior), follower (subordinate), and relationship (interpersonal relationship). Approach through the relationship between superiors and subordinates explains how interpersonal relationships occur. The dimensions and indicators used to measure the leader-member exchange are (Graen & Uhl-Bien, 1995), namely Respect, measured by indicators, Leaders know the problems and needs in the work of employees and Leaders recognize and appreciate the potential of employees. Trust can be measured by indicators such as the case of employees siding with their leaders and vice versa. Employees have confidence in their leaders so that employees defend and defend the leader's decisions even if the leader is not present to do so. Obligations are measured by indicators, such as in terms of the leader is willing to help employees in solving work problems, the leader is willing to guarantee employees who are in trouble with what they have. Effectiveness of the working relationship between leaders and employees.

Job Satisfaction

According to (Luthans, 2013), job satisfaction is a happy emotional state or positive emotion that comes from evaluating one's job or work experience. The dimensions and indicators used to measure job satisfaction according to (Luthans, 2013), namely the work itself, is measured by indicators such as the job is very interesting and employees feel satisfied with the job because they can make progress at work. Salary can be measured by indicators that employees are satisfied with the salary they receive and employees are satisfied with the benefits provided by the company. Promotion opportunities can be measured by indicators that employees are satisfied with their level of progress in the company, employees are satisfied with the opportunity to get a promotion, and employees are satisfied with the opportunity to get of promotion. Supervision can be measured by indicators, leaders always provide support to employees, leaders have high motivation, leaders give freedom to employees in making responsible decisions, and leaders are fair and honest with employees. Coworkers can be measured by the indicators that employees are satisfied with their co-workers, employees enjoy working with co-workers, co-workers are very cooperative, and co-workers provide support to fellow employees.

Job stress

Job stress according to (Mangkunegara, 2013) is a feeling of pressure experienced by employees in dealing with work. The dimensions of job stress according to (Mangkunegara, 2013), namely workload, through indicators, such as difficulty in working, excessive workload, and feeling tired. Working Time, with more work if the time is longer, less time at work, and no time to socialize. Feedback, such as rarely being praised and opinions not being heard.

Turnover Intention

Turnover intention is an employee's intention to stop working from his job voluntarily or to move from one workplace to another according to his own choice (Mobley, 2011). The dimensions and indicators used to measure turnover intentions according to (Mobley, 2011), namely by thinking about leaving (employees have thought about leaving the company and employees think they will leave work if there is a better opportunity, employees think about leaving because they feel bored and bored with work, and employees feel tired of their current job and think about moving to another place), Looking for alternative jobs (employees looking for job vacancies elsewhere, employees will leave the company if there is an offer from another company that provides a higher salary, and employees want to find a new work environment), Intention to leave (employees intend to leave their jobs because of the rewards they received is not appropriate, the employee intends to stop working because the work feels heavy, and the employee intends to leave the company because there is no career development).

Research Model and Hypothesis

Figure 1. Structural Model

- Ha1: LMX affects turnover intentions of hotel employees in Banda Aceh.
- H01: LMX does not affect turnover intentions of hotel employees in Banda Aceh.
- Ha2: Satisfaction affects turnover intentions of hotel employees in Banda Aceh.
- H02: Satisfaction does not affect turnover intentions of hotel employees in Banda Aceh.
- Ha3: Job stress affects turnover intentions of hotel employees in Banda Aceh.
- H03: Job stress does not affect turnover intentions of hotel employees in Banda Aceh.
- Ha4: LMX affects satisfaction of hotel employees in Banda Aceh.
- H04: LMX does not affect satisfaction of hotel employees in Banda Aceh.
- Ha5: LMX affects job stress of hotel employees in Banda Aceh.
- H05: LMX does not affect job stress of hotel employees in Banda Aceh.
- Ha6: Satisfaction mediates the effect of LMX on turnover intentions of hotel employees in Banda Aceh.
- H06: Satisfaction does not mediate the effect of LMX on turnover intentions of hotel employees in Banda Aceh.
- Ha7: Job stress mediates the effect of LMX on turnover intentions of hotel employees in Banda Aceh.
- H07: Job stress does not mediate the effect of LMX on turnover intentions of hotel employees in Banda Aceh.

III. Method

This research was conducted at three-star hotels in Banda Aceh, namely Ayani Hotel, Grand Nanggroe, Grand Permata Hati Hotel, and The Pade Hotel. The object that acted as an independent variable was LMX (X1), while turnover intention (Z), Job Satisfaction (Y1), and Job Stress (Y2) acted as dependent variables. This study presents the role of Job Satisfaction and Job Stress in mediating the effect of LMX on Turnover Intention. The population was all hotel employees, totaling 213 people. The way to determine the sample was to use the saturated sample technique.

IV. Result

Direct Effect Hypothesis

The results of the model analysis are shown below.

Figure 2. Structural Model

The results of hypotheses testing are directly presented below.

Table 1. Regression Result

		Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P
Job_Satisfaction	<--- LMX	,692	,085	7,956	***
Job_Stres	<--- LMX	-,689	,102	-7,312	***
Turnover_Intention	<--- LMX	-,372	,085	-3,870	***
Turnover_Intention	<--- Job_Stres	,198	,064	3,091	,002
Turnover_Intention	<--- Job_Satisfaction	-,386	,069	-5,559	***

Source: Processed Data (2022)

Table 2 formulates the following equation:

$$\text{Job Satisfaction} = 0,692 \text{ LMX}$$

$$\text{Job stress} = -0,689 \text{ LMX}$$

$$\text{Turnover Intention} = -0,372 \text{ LMX} + 0,198 \text{ Job Stres} - 0,386 \text{ Job Satisfaction}$$

LMX contribution to Satisfaction

The estimated parameter for testing the influence of LMX on satisfaction shows an estimated standard value of 0.692 or 69.2%, where if the LMX increases by 1%, satisfaction will increase by 69.2% with p 0.000 < 0.05. that p-value obtained meets the H2 acceptance, namely CR 7.956 (>1.96) and p < 0.05. This result reveals that the LMX affects Satisfaction. The magnitude of LMX on Satisfaction is 0.692 or 69.2%. This indicates that the better the LMX will have a positive and significant impact on increasing satisfaction.

This opinion is supported by (Bhatti, Islam, Mirza, & Ali, 2015) research which states that LMX is a trust-based relationship and employees with high LMX quality can get more support from their superiors. Therefore, they are more likely to get organizational-related benefits compared to employees who have low LMX qualities. LMX increases employee perceptions of the support provided by superiors which in turn contributes to employee satisfaction levels. Superiors need to maintain a good relationship with employees to increase satisfaction. If superiors keep their distance from employees and the relationship between employees is not harmonious, it causes employees to not be able to fulfill satisfaction.

LMX contribution to Job stress

The estimated parameter for testing the contribution of LMX on job stress shows that the standard value of the estimate is -0.689 or -68.9%, where if the LMX increases by 1%, the job stress variable will decrease by 68.9% with p 0.000 < 0.05. That p-value obtained meets the H3 acceptance, namely CR -7.312 (>1.96) and p < 0.05. This result explains that

the LMX affected job stress. The magnitude of LMX on Job Stress is -0.689 or -68.9%. This indicates that the higher the level of LMX reduces job stress.

In several studies on the LMX-stress relationship (Lagace, Castleberry, & Ridnour, 1993); (Snyder & Bruning, 1985); (Tanner & Castleberry, 1990); (Tanner, Dunn, & Chonko, 1993), where a high-quality LMX relationship will suppress the job stress of the supervisors involved. In high-quality LMX relationships provide emotional support, improve communication, and help them to keep their stress levels low. In contrast, those who enter into low-quality LMX relationships experience higher levels of stress because they do not receive support from their superiors when they feel that the demands of the job exceed their individual capacity to cope.

LMX contribution to Turnover intentions

The estimated parameter for testing the influence of LMX on turnover intentions shows the standard estimated value of -0.372 or -37.2%, where if the LMX increases by 1%, the turnover intentions variable will decrease by 37.2% with $p < 0.000 < 0.05$. That p-value obtained meets the H4 acceptance, namely CR -3.870 (>1.96) and $p < 0.05$. This result figures that the LMX affected Turnover Intention. The magnitude of LMX on Turnover intentions is -0.372 or -37.2%. This indicates that the higher the LMX, the higher the Turnover Intention.

(Saeed, Waseem, Sikander, & Rizwan, 2014) stated in their research that there is a significant relationship between LMX and turnover intention. If the relationship between superiors and employees is good, employees are more satisfied with their jobs and their turnover intentions will be lower. High LMX quality between employer and employee results in loyal and effective relationships. Managers must know how to improve relationships with employees so that they can understand each other and resulting in lower employee turnover intentions. If the relationship between employer and employee is poor, the employee has a greater intention to leave compared to high-quality LMX.

Job stress contribution to Turnover Intention

The estimated parameter of testing the contribution of job stress on turnover intentions shows an estimated standard value of 0.198 or 19.8%, where if job stress increases by 1% it will increase the turnover intentions variable by 19.8% with $p < 0.000 < 0.05$. That p-value obtained meets the H5 acceptance, namely CR 3.091 (>1.96) and $p < 0.05$. This result shows that the path coefficient between job stress and turnover intentions was obtained by the path coefficient value of 0.198 or 19.8%. This indicates that the higher the level of job stress, the higher the turnover intention.

(Zahra, Khan, Imran, & Aman, 2018) state that employees feel burdened by their work when there are many job demands, this creates stress among employees. Stress arises when employees are unable to cope with situations and pressure demands on their work. Job stress leads to the intention to leave the organization. The research of (Ahanian, Mirzaei, & Fard, 2016) shows that employees who experience stress in their work can endanger their health and cause intention to move. There is a positive and significant relationship between job stress and turnover intention. When job stress increases in intensity, turnover intention also increases.

Satisfaction contribution to Turnover Intention

The estimated parameter of testing the contribution of satisfaction on turnover intentions shows an estimated standard value of -0.386 or 38.6%, where if satisfaction increases by 1% it will reduce turnover intentions by 19.8% with $p < 0.000 < 0.05$. That p-value obtained meets the H6 acceptance, namely CR -5.559 (>1.96) and $p < 0.05$. This result explains that the path coefficient between Satisfaction and Turnover intentions obtained a value of -0.386 or -38.6%. This indicates that the higher the satisfaction, the higher the turnover intention.

(Saeed et al., 2014) state that satisfaction has an impact on turnover intention. High satisfaction is associated with low turnover intentions and low satisfaction leads to high turnover intentions. Satisfaction is the difference between the benefits an employee expects and the benefits he actually receives. The higher the difference between the expected benefits and the actual benefits, the higher the turnover intention. Organizations should work to minimize this difference to make their employees more satisfied to reduce their turnover intention. When employees are more satisfied then they maintain their productivity but if they are not satisfied then they will leave the organization.

Indirect Effect Hypothesis

Satisfaction Mediates the LMX contribution to Turnover Intention

This result figures that the path coefficient between the LMX on Satisfaction obtained the path coefficient value of 0.692 and was significant at 5%; while the path coefficient of Satisfaction to Turnover intentions is -0.386 and significant at 5%. The path coefficient between LMX and Turnover intentions is -0.372 and is significant at 5%. Because of the indirect influence of LMX on Turnover intentions mediated by Satisfaction which has a Sobel test result of $-4.61 > 1.96$

and is at a significance level of 5%, it indicates that there is an indirect influence between LMX on Turnover intentions mediated by Satisfaction partially (partially mediation).

High-quality LMX involves a high level of trust between parties, and emotional support for group members (Dansereau, Graen, & Haga, 1975); (Dienesch & Liden, 1986). When superiors pay attention and give full support to their employees, it can affect the employee's satisfaction. According to (Chen, Cheng, & Chien, 2010), a person is satisfied with his job if the job meets his expectations. Higher satisfaction tends to result in lower employee turnover rates, whereas lower satisfaction results in lower employee turnover rates. Based on the description above, it concludes that satisfaction mediates the effect of LMX on turnover intention.

Job Stress Mediates the LMX contribution to Turnover Intention

This result reveals that the path coefficient between LMX on Job Stress obtained a path coefficient value of -0.689 and was significant at 5%; while the path coefficient of Job stress on Turnover intentions is 0.198 and significant at 5%. The path coefficient between LMX on Turnover intentions is -0.372 and is significant at 5%. Because of the indirect influence of LMX on Turnover intentions mediated by Job Stress which has a Sobel test result of -2.81 > 1.96 and is at a significance level of 5%, it indicates that there is an indirect influence between LMX on Turnover intentions mediated by job stress partially (partially mediation).

Job stress affects employee satisfaction which leads to low performance and intention to leave work (Applebaum, Fowler, Fiedler, Osinubi, & Robson, 2010). The LMX literature suggests that high-quality LMX can affect satisfaction (Scandura & Graen, 1984); (Sparrowe & Liden, 1997). (Bauer et al., 2006) stated in their research on the relationship between turnover intentions and LMX, that members who have low exchange quality will have a weak relationship with their leader, so they have a greater intention to leave compared to the quality of the LMX relationship.

Conclusion of Direct and Indirect Contribution Effect

Table 2. Conclusion of The Influences

No	Description	Direct influence X to Z	Indirect influence	Total Effect	Note
1.	Testing the influence of LMX on Turnover intentions through Satisfaction	$(-0,372)^2 = 0,1383$	0,692 (-0,386) = -0,2671	-0,1288	Direct > Indirect
2.	Testing the influence of LMX on Turnover intentions through Job Stress	$(-0,372)^2 = 0,1383$	-0,689 (0,198) = -0,1364	0,0019	Direct > Indirect

Table 3 describes that the direct contribution of LMX on Turnover intentions is 0.1383, while the indirect contribution is -0.2671. This indicates that the direct influence is greater than the indirect contribution. The direct contribution of LMX on Turnover intentions is 0.1383, while the indirect contribution is -0.1383. This shows that the direct contribution is greater than the indirect contribution.

V. Conclusion

This study reveals that :

1. LMX positively affects Satisfaction, meaning that the better the LMX that is established, it will increase the Satisfaction of hotel employees in Banda Aceh.
2. LMX negatively affects Job Stress, meaning that the better the LMX that is established, the lower the level of job stress for hotel employees in Banda Aceh.
3. LMX negatively affects Turnover Intention, meaning that the better the LMX is, the lower the Turnover intentions level for hotel employees in Banda Aceh.
4. Job stress positively affects Turnover Intention, meaning that the higher the Job stress felt by the employees, the higher the Turnover intentions of hotel employees in Banda Aceh.
5. Satisfaction positively affects Turnover Intention, meaning that the higher the Satisfaction felt by the employees, the lower the Turnover intentions of hotel employees in Banda Aceh.
6. Satisfaction partially mediates the influence of LMX on Turnover Intention. This indicates that the LMX can directly influence Turnover intentions without going through Satisfaction.
7. Job stress partially mediates the effect of LMX on Turnover Intention. This indicates that the LMX can directly influence Turnover intentions without going through job stress.

This finding proves that the model of decreasing turnover intention for hotel employees in Banda Aceh is a function of increasing LMX which can contribute to increasing job satisfaction and reducing job stress. Some of the facts found in the field from the results of this study are as follows.

1. Several statements from respondents can be input for improvement by the hotel, namely, they feel that the leadership has not appreciated and recognized the potential they have, the leader does not know the problems and needs in the work of their subordinates, and the employees feel the working relationship between the leadership and subordinates have not run effectively.
2. Several statements from respondents can be input for improvement by the hotel, namely the salary given is not following what is done, employees are not satisfied with the benefits provided, they have not had the opportunity to get career advancement, have not had the opportunity to get a raise, and employees think the boss has not been fair to them.
3. All indicators on the job stress variable are at a high level so it is hoped that the right policy will solve the difficulties in working, too much workload, feeling easily tired, limited time given, lack of time to socialize, rarely given awards, and opinions. which is rarely heard by the leadership.
4. All indicators of turnover intentions are also in a high position, marked by the desire to leave, seeing opportunities to leave, feeling bored and bored with work, tired of current work, trying to find other job vacancies, waiting for other job offers that have higher salaries, trying to find a new work environment, the rewards received are not appropriate, the work is considered too heavy, and there is no career development. All of these situations require real and persistent actions and policies, such as comprehensive planning, organizing, and monitoring reforms. Besides that, the leadership is also expected to be more open to hearings between employees so that all complaints and expectations of employees can be accommodated by the company.

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